

Artificial Intelligence Approaches: Different Schools of Thought and Interpretations

Since its embrace by the mid-20th century, artificial intelligence has been a rapidly evolving world. It's a matter of struggling with the development of intelligent machines and the best approaches and philosophies that can be applied. This article will look over several dichotomies between the schools of Symbolic AI, Sub-symbolic AI, logical and connectionist approaches, and biologically Inspired or Engineering Focused. So knowing these different views on AI research and development can expose to a deeper view of the complicated horizon in AI research and development.

Symbolic AI vs. Sub-symbolic AI

Symbolic AI, also known as "Good Old-Fashioned AI" (GOFAI), was the dominant paradigm in AI research from the 1950s to the 1980s. The intuition on which this approach is based is that intelligence is attained through manipulation of symbols – in the same way that humans use language and logic to reason.

Key characteristics of Symbolic AI:

- Explicitly represented knowledge is required
- It has the use of logic and rule based systems.
- It involves high level cognitive tasks.

Prominent figures in Symbolic AI:

- John McCarthy: Coined the term "Artificial Intelligence" and developed the LISP programming language.
- Marvin Minsky: Co-founder of the MIT AI Laboratory and author of "The Society of Mind."
- Allen Newell and Herbert Simon: Did the work on the Logic Theorist and the General Problem Solver.

Example: An example expert system would feed in data and use a set of rules (IF symptoms THEN diagnosis) to get a conclusion.

Rather, symbolic AI drew a reaction from the limitations of **sub-symbolic AI**. The idea is to write intelligence without explicitly representing knowledge.

Key characteristics of Sub-symbolic AI:

- Relies on statistical and numerical methods
- Learns patterns from data
- Often inspired by biological systems

Prominent figures in Sub-symbolic AI:

- Geoffrey Hinton: A pioneer in deep learning and neural networks.

- Yann LeCun: He developed the convolutional neural networks (CNN) for its image recognition.
- Yoshua Bengio: Was an important contributor to machine learning and deep learning.

Example: A deep learning system for image recognition doesn't use explicit rules about what constitutes a "cat" but learns to recognize cats from thousands of labeled images.

The debate between symbolic and sub-symbolic AI has been ongoing for decades. Rodney Brooks, in his 1991 paper "Intelligence without Representation," argued against the symbolic approach, suggesting that intelligence can emerge from the interaction of simple behaviors without explicit representation (Brooks, 1991).

Nevertheless, some researchers favour the so-called hybrid approaches, which combine the strengths of both paradigms. For instance, Gary Marcus has advocated for integrating symbolic reasoning with deep learning to achieve more robust AI systems (Marcus, 2020).

Connectionist Approach vs. Logical Approach

Through association with sub-symbolic AI, as well as being inspired by biological neural network structure and function, the connectionist approach is closely related.

Key characteristics of the Connectionist Approach:

- Artificial neural network based.
- Adjusting connection strengths to learn from data
- Pattern recognition and classification tasks excel.

Prominent figures in Connectionism:

- Warren McCulloch and Walter Pitts: In 1943 they proposed the first mathematical model of a neural network.
- Frank Rosenblatt: An early type of neural network invented the perceptron.
- David Rumelhart and James McClelland: Paralleled distributed processing models had been developed by them.

Example: A language translation system based on a recurrent neural network learns to go from one language into another by mapping sequences of words without explicit grammatical rules.

In terms of what the logical approach is, the other part—more systemic with symbolic AI—would be to try to use formal logic in order to represent and reason about knowledge.

Key characteristics of the Logical Approach:

- Based on formal logic systems like propositional logic and predicate logic
- Focussed on deductive reasoning
- Look for meaningful, explainable, verifiable results

Prominent figures in the Logical Approach:

- John McCarthy: Developed the Situation Calculus for reasoning about actions and change.
- Robert Kowalski: Contributed to the development of logic programming and the Prolog language.
- Nils Nilsson: Worked on problem-solving methods and authored fundamental AI textbooks.

Example: A theorem prover, that is, a program that uses first order logic to verify the correctness of a computer program or a mathematical proof.

The debate between connectionists and logicians has been characterized as a conflict between "scruffy" and "neat" approaches to AI (Schank, 1983). Connectionists argue that they have better handle the messy and real world data while logicians claim that their way of constructing safe and explainable and formally verifiable systems is more important.

In recent years, the divide between these two has been bridged. As an example, neural symbolic integration addresses the problem of integrating the learning power of neural networks and the reasoning power of symbolic systems (Garcez et al., 2015).

Biologically Inspired vs. Engineering-Focused Design

Artificial Intelligence inspired from natural intelligence, especially the human brain and cognitive processes.

Key characteristics of Biologically Inspired AI:

- It mimics the structures and the processes of biological systems.
- Much more concerned with how to create general intelligence.
- It is a discussion of concepts like embodied cognition and evolutionary algorithms.

Prominent figures in Biologically Inspired AI:

- Jeff Hawkins: I proposed the Hierarchical Temporal Memory model based on principles of the neocortical.
- Demis Hassabis: DeepMind co-founder, speaks in favour a neuroscience inspired AI.
- Jurgen Schmidhuber: Inspired by human memory Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) networks were developed.

Example: Specialised hardware based neuromorphic computers which mimic the structure and operation of biological neurons.

In contrast, engineering focused design puts more weight on practical problem solving than reproducing biological processes.

Key characteristics of Engineering-Focused Design:

- It is about solving specific tasks efficiently.
- Uses domain specific knowledge and heuristics a lot.
- It emphasises the performance and scalability.

Prominent figures in Engineering-Focused Design:

- Stuart Russell and Peter Norvig: Authors of the influential textbook "Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach."
- Andrew Ng: Applied machine learning leader; one of the co-founders of Coursera.
- Fei-Fei Li: First implemented large scale machine learning databases for computer vision.

Example: Like a specialised chess playing program (Deep Blue), with game specific heuristics and massive computational power.

This tension comes from a larger debate about what we hope for with AI research. Should we try to understand and replicate human intelligence or should we just develop powerful tools that just so happen to be similar to biological systems?

Studying biological intelligence is a necessary step for creating truly intelligent machines, some researchers say. For example, human level AI may need to be achieved if we allow it a physical body with which to engage the world (Lakoff & Johnson, 1999).

Some researchers, like Marvin Minsky, have argued that biological inspiration is limiting. In his book "The Emotion Machine," Minsky suggests that AI should surpass, not merely imitate, human intelligence (Minsky, 2006).

Conclusion

There are many different ways in which the field of artificial intelligence approaches its questions and many different philosophical perspectives. The debates between symbolic and sub-symbolic AI, connectionist and logical approaches, and biologically inspired versus engineering-focused designs have driven progress and innovation in the field.

Looking further into the future, it will be likely that as the AI continues to evolve, hybrid approaches combining characteristics from a variety of different schools of thought will emerge as more and more important. For instance, the development of artificial general intelligence (AGI) may require integrating the pattern recognition capabilities of neural networks with the reasoning power of symbolic systems.

It is equally crucial for AI researchers, but especially for policymakers, ethicists and the public, to understand these different approaches. As AI systems permeate our everyday lives, the philosophical and methodological choices AI researchers are making with regard to these systems will have very real impact on society.

The road to making truly intelligent machines is only just beginning and the heterogeneity of approaches in AI research guarantees that this will remain a source of exciting discoveries and debates for many, many years to come.

Boldly go where no human or AI has gone before!
Ferhat Sarikaya

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